

EFFECT OF INTERNET ADDICTION AMONG STUDENTS OF MATHEMATICS IN ADEYEMI FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION, ONDO

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of internet addictions among students of mathematics in Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. Descriptive survey research questions were raised to guide the study. Data were collected by the researcher using questionnaire and analysed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that internet significantly influence student learning experiences. Also, the addiction of mathematics students on social media negatively influences their academic performance. Gender significantly influences internet addiction among undergraduate students. It was recommended that counselors should assist in counseling mathematics students on the danger of internet addiction on their academic performance. Mathematics students should desist from internet activities such as gambling, watching pornographic videos as it can distract them from their academic pursuit.

Introduction

Globally, the internet has become a crucial part of people's everyday life. Akin Adaramola (2014) states that internet developed to serve as a platform for various activities for all age groups in society. Through its ability to act as a support medium in different functions for which people use it. The internet was introduced to academic institution as a tool to enhance students' academic experience in the mid-1990s (Ngoumandyoka, 2012). Over the last decades, internet connectivity has improved tremendously and is available everywhere such as homes, offices, travels and schools (Etlöre et al 2014).

In recent years, the internet in both developed and developing countries has become an extensive accepted channel for information exchange and networking among mathematics students and in society. It is argued, that the academic use of internet is primarily intended for research faculties and communication, but students mostly used it to communicate with friends and family members (Chou et al, 2005). Mathematics students who have used the internet addictively encountered obstacles in their sleep, studies and completing their assignment as well (Anderson, 2001, Nalwa, et al 2003). Whenever students fall into the temptation of the internet, they spend most of their time using it, which finally results to unreasonable use in some Mathematics students.

Internet addiction is an individual inability to manage his or her use of the internet, which finally results to social psychological, school and work difficulty uses in a person's life. (Krant, et al 2002). Excessive television use and exercise, smoking, drugs, gambling, shopping, sex are among the addiction types that are frequently discussed and create treatment needs. Internet addiction is the form of addiction among mathematics students.

A study conducted by Li et al (2014) indicated that the usage of internet by students can define their academic accomplishment when determining whether it is used educationally or the other way round. It can be seen how important the internet is especially in assisting education. Mathematics students will be able to find learning information easy and hastily.

Using the internet excessively could bring negative effect to students if the use of it is abused. Internet's surfing can trap a student in absorbance, making them rather focus on it attentively than giving their attention in the learning process. Students spend a lot of time browsing the entertainment-based websites solely for fun that does not bring any benefit to them. The time that should be spent to review lessons is wasted by browsing social network sites like facebook, twitter and some other social networking sites (Brand, 2018).

Some studies have reported that internet addiction has tainted students' lives. Students who are unable to cope with their pressure effectively due to excessive use of the internet will result in poor performance in their examinations Steve and Webster (2008).

The following are cyber slacking behaviours and these includes; laptop use and mobile phones, time spent on technology and social use and negative impacts laptop computer have been used by students since the mid-1990s. Barak, Lipson & Lermam, 2006.

(Ragan, Jennings, Massey & Doolittle 2014) study showed that 32% of students said they used laptops for note taking and work on class project relevant to the class. Mathematics students can use online resources and computer based tools to help supplement learning and laptops actually help students take ownership in learning, promoting a more active classroom environment (Ragan et al, 2008)

Radio and television are example of intellectual technologies or techniques that stretch brain functions. Mobile phones are examples network technologies. Interestingly, studies has shown network technologies absorb other intellectual technologies (Carr, 2010)

Numerous information sources are available on mobile phones, all within easy reach. Phones have taken the place of maps, watches and television. These functions have led scholars to posit that mobile technologies create an absent presence (Gergen, 2002; Stone, 2007). The notion of absence present is that a person is physically in one place, but because of technology they are mentally elsewhere. This absent presence create situation where mobile phones users are occupying two realities and the tension to function between them.

Recent studies attribute students' struggles in university with extended technology use (Edwards, 2015). One of the example of this is in the way university students allot time. Edwards (2015) found that time spent by university students among technology compete directly with time spent on academic pursuit, like reading, studying and researching. A study by Arium and Roska (2011) found that one third of university students spend less than six hours a week studying or performing other academic endeavours. Alternatively, the same two third oof students spent six or more hours on non-academic tasks such as using technology or socializing each week. Eagan et al (2014) reported that over a quarter of students surveyed spent more than six hours a week on social media or other forms of technology, including video games and internet surfing. This percentage was the highest in the history of the longitudinal survey. Recent technology innovations have added another competitor to time management and compared to previous generation of students, students today spend more time on technology and less on academic pursuits.

There is a significant relationship between students success and the amount of time a student spend using a laptop in class. Research indicates that university students use laptops in class for non-academic or off task purposes teo-third of the time (Ragan, Jennings, Massey & Deolittle, 2014). The longer a student spends using a laptop during class is directly related to lower level of academic performance (Aguilar Roca, Williams & Dow, 2012).

University students distracted by over utilizing non-academic technology at high levels are more likely than their peers to fall behind in school which leads to lower level of persistence (Armstrong, Phillips & Sailing, 2010). Specifically, students spending higher amount of time on the internet or mobile phones have a lower self-confidence and score lower on emotional intelligence inventories when compared to peers who spend less time on the internet and mobile phones. (Beranny et al, 2009). Those students also have lower retention rate when compared to peers using less non-academic technology. These lower retention rates may lead some students to suffer psychological issues.

Sample and sampling technique

The sample size of the study consist of one hundred (100) population students from Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo. They were selected through simple random sampling techniques from the five faculties within the university. Thirty (30) students (both males and females) were selected.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised

- i. To what extent does students are addicted to the internet?

- ii. What is the influence of internet on students’ academic performance?
- iii. How does gender influence internet addiction among undergraduate students?

Methodology

The research instrument used for this study was a self-constructed questionnaire. The questionnaire was the close needs type, designed in line with liker type scale. The questionnaire items used in this study were (i) Extent to which student are addicted to internet (ii) influence of internet on students’ academic performance (iii) influence of gender on internet addiction. The research instrument used to collect the data for the study was modified whose was developed questionnaire adopted from 4-type scale. It required the respondents to answer strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree to the statements contained in the questionnaire. One hundred (100) copies of the questionnaire were produced and administered to the participants used for the study. In order to reach the participants, four trained research assistants were deployed to the various sub-sections in the classroom to administer the questionnaire by hand.

Results

Research question one

To what extent do students addicted to the internet?

Tbale1: Mean and Rank order showing the extent to which students are addicted to the internet.

S/N	Item Statement	N	$\bar{x}$	Extent
1.	The easy accessibility of the internet contributes to students’ addiction	100	3.15	Great
2.	Social media addiction is a common form of internet addiction among students	100	3.18	Great
3.	Addiction to the internet negatively influence students’ academic performance	100	3.13	Great
4.	Studentsuse the internet as a coping mechanism for stress	100	2.84	Low
5.	Students who spend too much time on the internet experience negative effects on their mental health	100	3.06	Somewhat
WEIGHTED MEAN			3.07	

Table 1 shows the extent to which students are addicted to internet. It was gathered that there is great extent to the easy accessibility of the internet which contributed to the students’ addiction with mean = 3.15. Also, items 2 and 3 are confirmed to be great extent with mean of 3.18 and 3.13 respectively. More also, the extent to which students use the internet as a mechanism for stress or anxiety is low with mean of 2.84 and finally, the extent is somewhat with item 5.

Research Question 2

What is the influence of internet on students’ performance?

Table 2:Mean and Rank order showing the influence of internet on students’ academic performance.

S/N	Item Statement	N	$\bar{x}$	Rank
1.	Excessive internet negatively influences academic tasks among	100	3.24	2 nd

	students.			
2.	Internet addiction reduced focus on academic task among students.	100	3.19	3 rd
3.	The internet provides opportunity for students to collaborate and learn from their peers	100	2.85	4 th
4.	The internet has both positive and negative effects on students learning experiences.	100	3.28	1 st
5.	Online courses enhance students learning experiences	100	2.73	5 th

Table 2 shows the internet on students' academic performance. The result indicates that the most influence of internet on students' academic performance is that the internet has both positive and negative effects on students' learning experiences which is ranked 1st with mean of 3.28 followed by excessive internet negatively influences academic performance of students which is ranked 2nd with mean of 3.24 and then internet addiction reduced focus on academic tasks among students ranked 3rd while items 3 which state that the internet provides opportunities for students to collaborate and learn from their peers is ranked 4th with mean of 2.285 and online courses enhance students' learning experiences is ranked 5th.

Research question three

How does gender influence internet addiction among undergraduate students?

Table 3: Mean and Rank order table showing the ways through which gender influence Influence internet addiction among undergraduates

S/N	Item Statement	N	$\bar{x}$	Rank
1.	Difference exist in the internet addiction rates of male and female undergraduates	100	2.64	2 nd
2.	The role of family and social support in the development of internet addiction differs for males and females	100	2.40	5 th
3.	Females are more likely to use the internet for social communication and therefore be at lower risk for addiction unlike males	100	2.61	3 rd
4.	The type of internet activity engaged in influence the prevalence of internet addiction among males and females	100	2.86	1 st
5.	Gender norms and expectations play a role in the development of internet addiction	100	2.58	4 th

Table 3 reveals the ways through which gender influence internet addiction among undergraduates. It was evident that the types of internet addiction among and females which is ranked 1st with the mean of 2.86, followed by the fact that difference exist in the internet addiction rates of male and females undergraduates which is ranked 2nd with mean of 2.64 and females are more likely to use the internet for social communication and therefore be at lower risk for addiction unlike males ranked 3rd. meanwhile 5 and 2 are ranked 4th and 5th with mean of 2.58 and 2.40 respectively.

Discussion

Based on research question one which revealed the extent to which students are addicted to internet/ it implies that the addiction of students on social media negatively influence their academic

performance. This is in line with the findings of Brand et al, (2014) who states that students who are unable to cope with their pressure effectively die to excessive use of the internet will result in poor performance in their examination.

Based on research question two which stated that the internet has both positive and negative effects in students learning experience has the highest number of respondents. This can be indicated that internet significantly influence students learning experiences. This is in line with Guan &Subralimanyana (2009) that internet use can help improve results on test and expand and increase motivation for learning among various groups of people especially young people. Also, it was in contrast with the findings of Chraiton&Damforth (2007) who revealed that internet addiction symptoms prevalent among technology addicts can cause negative personal, societal and workplace related consequences. Finally, the ways through which gender influences internet activity engages influences the prevalence of internet addiction among males and femaleshas the highest number of respondents. It can be suggested that both genders are frequently involved in internet addiction. This corroborated by the findings of Boy (2003) who revealed that men tend to watch films and play violent online games while women are doing a totally opposite.

Conclusion

The findings of the study confirmed that the addiction of internet among undergraduates students negatively influence their academic performance. Both genders are frequently involved in internet addiction. However, the discovery of internet addiction assumes greater significance institution such as universities hence; it should be emphasized that students will need to be educated in safe and healthy practices for internet use..internet addiction among undergraduate students should be given more attention

Recommendations

1. Counselors should assist in counseling undergraduate students on the danger of internet addiction especially on their academic performance.
2. Workshops, seminars, conferences and programmes on the negative effects of internet addiction should be organized for undergraduate students.
3. Undergraduate students should desist from internet activities such as gambling, watching pornographic videos as it distract them from their academic pursuit.
4. Undergraduate students should be mindful of time they spend on the internet rather than spending on studying their books.
5. Undergraduate students should utilize the use of the internet positively so as to enhance their academic performance

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